

NEW PERSPECTIVES ON E-MENTORING MODELS IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract

In the context of COVID-19 pandemic, virtual learning environments (VLEs) and virtual learning management systems usage increased due to social isolation measures and the introduction of new e-learning platforms and instruments. However, the utility and relevance of this approach is questionable for many education experts and particularly practitioners in the context of mentoring or pedagogical practicum. Our study is focusing on the emergence of new e-Mentoring models in higher education and particularly on the misconceptions related to the use of learning management systems in mentoring.

Keywords: virtual learning environments; virtual learning systems; e-mentoring; mentoring; appreciative inquiry; SOAR model

Mentoring and particularly e-mentoring has become, in the recent years, one of the most important strategies to unlock educational and organizational potential. The functions and capabilities of the modern computers, tablets and smartphones that are used by vast segments of the population represent a bridge that can be used by educational institutions to support the implementation of virtual learning management systems and virtual learning environments. Inside a virtual learning community, teachers and mentors can use new mentoring models, digital curricula and strategies, techniques and models that are better suited to interactions in a digital world.

Using a modern LMS has a lot of advantages such as (Strungă and Bunăiașu, 2019):

- a) Reducing the amount of time needed to efficiently communicate with the group and inside the group (e.g. classroom);
- b) Using advanced features of cutting-edge educational software: online classes, online shared library, subgroups, etc.
- c) Analysing student behavior and taking corrective measures in a very short time;
- d) The extension of the learning activities outside school and class; the resources can be used from a variety of devices and environments.
- e) A better understanding of learning difficulties;
- f) Supporting the students with an individualized curriculum and easily creating project-based subgroups (teams of one or more students working on the same tasks);
- g) Using modern computer-based evaluation strategies that offer more transparency to both students and parents. The assignments can be more easily assessed and the teacher can develop flexible educational pathways to remediate any kind of issues that are negatively influencing student's achievement.

The specialists in the field of mentoring and e-mentoring highlighted the importance of a new paradigm that was developed during the '80s by David Cooperrider and Suresh Srivastva called Appreciative Inquiry (Cooperrider and Srivastva 1987). The new paradigm focuses more on the values, beliefs and capabilities of an organization when it's 'at its best'. Furthermore, AI (Appreciative Inquiry) is also encompassing the collective understandings around and what makes up the best in people (Cooperrider and Whitney, 1999). From an organizational standpoint, the focus is no more on problem solving and identifying issues that do not work but instead on the best qualities, attributes, values of an organization and/or individual. Based on the AI approach, the 4D Model was proposed with four steps: Discovery, Dream, Design, Destiny (Kessler, 2013). These steps could also constitute the basis for a virtual learning management system, facilitating an educational strategy that combines individual and team work to achieve individual and group success. The entire mentoring program can be devised by having in mind the 4D AI Model, using digital tools on a virtual learning management system such as Moodle or Google Classroom.

Discovery

In this first step, the participants are asked to identify the best qualities, practices and values of an educational organization, group or community. Past successes can be analyzed and discussed in order to share what enabled them in the first place. Many times, the participants are focused only on the perceived weaknesses of the organization, on what is missing, thus neglecting what has been done in a valuable and efficient way.

In the context of this step, an Appreciative Interview Protocol was proposed, with the following structure (Ludema et al, 2006):

1. Think of a time in your entire experience with your organization when you have felt most excited, most engaged, and most alive. What were the forces and factors that made it a great experience? What was it about you, others, and your organization that made it a peak experience for you?
2. What do you value most about yourself, your work, and your organization?
3. What are your organization's best practices (ways you manage, approaches, traditions)?
4. What are the unique aspects of your culture that most positively affect the spirit, vitality, and effectiveness of your organization and its work?
5. What is the core factor that "give life" to your organization?
6. What are the three most important hopes you have to heighten the health and vitality of your organization for the future?

Dream

The second step is focused on imagining different positive scenarios for the organization. Instead of analyzing what is missing or lacking, the participants are asked to create positive outlooks and ideal setups for the organization. For instance, participants could brainstorm and discuss in small teams new models, strategies, resources, products, topics related to the organizational activity. These ideas may also be highlighted in a mindmap in order to use it for the next steps.

Design

In the third step, the participants focus on the ideas selected in the previous step. The aim is to create a shared representation and image of a successful organization. This step is many times neglected in other strategies of mentoring but is essential in the process of values alignment inside an organization. Different people can have different visions of what success is and these differences can constitute a source of conflict, if not discussed openly.

Destiny

Formerly called Delivery, the last step aims to transform the vision that was discussed and collectively assumed in action, by using a concrete strategy or action plan. Ludema emphasizes that in this step, the accent is on constructing a future “through innovation and action”. In this step, the methodology, techniques and instruments are discussed and analyzed based on the possible impact on organizational success.

Based on the success of Appreciative Inquiry and Appreciative Interview, Stavros and her collaborators proposed a new framework for strategic planning – SOAR which stands for Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations and Results (Stavros et al, 2003). The main difference from the more commonly used SWOT model is the accent put on the positive approach to change (represented here by aspirations and results).

<i>Strategic Inquiry</i>	<i>Appreciative Inquiry</i>
STRENGTHS <i>What are the greatest assets and values in our organization?</i>	ASPIRATIONS <i>What is our preferred future scenarios and vision?</i>
OPPORTUNITIES <i>What are the best possible opportunities?</i>	RESULTS <i>What are the measurable results?</i>

Table 1. The SOAR Framework (adapted from Stavros et al, 2003).

Stavros and her collaborators also propose a four step approach to using SOAR. The first step is *Inquiry* as defined in the conventional AI paradigm and focuses on the best assets, values of an organization, process or relationship. The second step focuses on *Imagination*, which is correlated with the Dream stage from the 4D AI model, in which the participants identify the preferred future scenarios for team work. The third stage *Innovation* aims to develop a strategy to breakdown deliverables, objectives, methods, timeframes and resources. In the last step, *Inspire*, the participants are asked to propose systems that offer incentives, recognition and rewards (Stavros et al, 2003).

In conclusion, we recommend several research directions related to the use of SOAR framework and more generally, Appreciative Inquiry in mentoring and the development of virtual learning management systems:

1. How can we better integrate the LMS with new organizational paradigms such as Appreciative Inquiry?
2. What are the ways to better develop a virtual learning community by making use of the most recent mentoring models, methods, and strategies?
3. How can we implement the SOAR framework to mentoring relationships in virtual environments?
4. What is the impact of applying SOAR on individual and collective educational performances in virtual learning management systems?
5. What are the best practices of using Appreciative Inquiry in educational large-scale projects and initiatives?
6. What are the best research instruments that can be used to measure the impact of applying the SOAR framework relatively to other models that are currently used on strategic management and educational leadership?

Appreciative Inquiry and SOAR framework can be successfully used in mentoring and strategic management as a very important and useful approach, especially in the context of the new digital tools and platforms that are being used in schools and universities. The focus on the positive aspects of a community and culture offers at the same time a way to collectively construct the future and strengthen, in the same time, the human and educational relationships.

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